

Cognitive Models of Studying Polysemy of Linguistic Terms in English

Dalieva Madina Khabibullaevna¹, N.Z.Valieva²,

¹Associate Professor, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

²Master's student, Uzbekistan State University of World Language

ABSTRACT

The article discusses issues based on analyzing cognitive models of studying polysemy of linguistic terms in English. Using the same word in different meanings is a natural mental operation for a person. The human brain has the ability to store quite a lot of information material. Polysemy in the English language makes it impossible to choose an appropriate method of memorizing words. Therefore, it is worth considering and learning English words not in isolation, but always in context. Let these be phrases or even whole sentences that consecrate one or another meaning of a polysemantic word. The meanings of a polysemantic word are actually present in the mind.

Keywords: polysemy, word, linguistic terms phenomena, meaning.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of polysemy occurs in many language systems, and in the English language it manifests itself very acutely. The linguistic term for this concept is polysemy - the presence of several meanings for one word or lexical unit. There are many more polysemantic words in English than in Russian and Uzbek languages. Here, depending on the context and lexical environment, most words in common vocabulary can change their meaning and semantics. Learning English words should be inextricably linked with memorizing various phrases in which they carry a certain meaning. The word is the basic unit of language, creating an idea of things in the real world and the psychological life of a person. Each word has its own meaning. A word that has no meaning is not a word. And this definition is the most important aspect of the word.

By studying the features of the world and highlighting in it a relatively complete set of elements (situations, states of affairs) and the individual elements included in them, displaying them in their consciousness and forming linguistic designations, people deal with many innumerable phenomena of the world and the perceptions of these phenomena. At the same time, the language tends to limit the number of its elementary sign units (words, morphemes) and the syntactic methods of “packaging” the transmitted information used when creating constructive sign units (phrases, sentences, texts).

Polysemy is characteristic equally of both words and morphemes (both root and affix), it is also inherent in constructive objects (phrases, sentences, texts). Polysemy is characteristic of most words (both significant and auxiliary), since this can easily be detected by opening an explanatory dictionary of any of the languages of the world [3].

There are many more polysemantic English words than Russian ones. Here, depending on the context and lexical environment, most words in common vocabulary can change their meaning and semantics.

Based on this, when translating a sentence, it is necessary to choose only one from many meanings of a word. When selecting this meaning, it is necessary to proceed from the general content of the thought contained in this sentence, as well as from the general content of the text being translated.

But even when a word is used consistently in the same grammatical function, the meaning is revealed only if it is in connection with other words and often depends on preceding and subsequent sentences.

Polysemy appears due to the fact that the language system is more limited in comparison with the infinite variety of realities, as a result of which the language is forced to distribute every possible abundance of meanings into certain categories of basic concepts. It is necessary to distinguish between all possible uses of the

lexical-semantic variant of a word. Typically, a new meaning occurs by transferring one of the existing words to a new object or situation.

This is how figurative meanings are formed. They are based on the similarity of objects or the relationship of one object with another.

The polysemy of words is so great and multifaceted that the problems of lexicology are to a certain extent related to it.

DISCUSSIONS

Polysemy in the English language makes it impossible to choose an appropriate method for memorizing words. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account and remember English words not in isolation, but always in context. Let these be phrases or even whole sentences that consecrate one or another meaning of a polysemantic word. In this case, the role of connecting function words, such as prepositions, conjunctions, or their absence, is great. In linguistics, there are a number of attempts to establish a classification of parts of speech (lexico-grammatical categories), which meets the basic requirements of logical classification, i.e. based on only one principle. These attempts failed. The classification of parts of speech remains controversial; There are disagreements among linguists regarding the number and composition of parts of words.

G. Sweet is the author of the first scientific grammar of the English language. For the first time, it was he who divided the parts of speech into two main groups - changeable and unchangeable. In this regard, he considers morphological properties as the fundamental principle of classification. In the group of changeables (“declinables”), he adhered to the traditional division - nouns, adjectives, verbs. While Sweet combined adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions and interjections into a group of unchangeables (“indeclinables”).

G. Sweet saw inconsistencies in the morphological and syntactic properties of parts of speech; but his attempt to create a coherent grouping led to the fact that, according to syntactic characteristics, categories that were lexically and

morphologically combined were fragmented, and, on the other hand, fragments of categories that were lexically and morphologically dissimilar were combined [8].

O. Jespersen, a Danish linguist and author of *The Philosophy of Grammar*, the multi-volume *Grammar of Modern English* and several other works, understood the difficulties associated with reconciling the two basic principles (morphology and syntax), even without taking into account lexical meaning. Jespersen proposed a dual system: along with the description of traditional parts of speech, taking into account their morphological design and conceptual (conceptual) content, the role of the same classes in syntactic combinations (sentences and phrases) is analyzed:

- this or that word may be primary, i.e. to be the core of a phrase, or the subject of a sentence;
- secondary, i.e. directly determining the primary
- tertiary, i.e. subordinate to the secondary [2].

According to E.S. Kubryakova, parts of speech are a deeply anthropocentric phenomenon. The reason parts of speech were created was to distinguish between different types of linguistic information about the world around us. It was necessary to distinguish between such entities as action, participants in action, place and time of action, direction of action [5].

The English language, with its limited number of inflections (inflectional suffixes) and derivational suffixes, belongs to the analytical languages. In the English language, function words are widely used as analytical tools, that is, words that clarify the grammatical category of semantic words (nouns, adjectives, verbs, etc.) and serve as a means of recognizing parts of speech, expressing case endings and forming verb conjugation forms.

The entire vocabulary of the English language is divided into certain lexical and grammatical classes, traditionally called parts of speech.

The most generally accepted classification of words according to lexical and semantic properties is to divide them into significant and functional words. The

main difference between these classes is that the significant parts of speech perform a representative function, indicating the surrounding reality, namely, they serve as names of individual objects, facts, and phenomena [1].

Significant words can form a separate statement and constitute the broadest and most fundamental type of words. In the same type of words, function words serve the “sphere of communicative speech activity.” They express an attitude towards the extra-linguistic world when used with significant words.

Morphological properties are also added to them to a certain extent: only significant parts of speech have inflection. However, in significant parts of speech, not all have an inflection paradigm; therefore, morphological features are not limited in all cases [6].

Functional parts of speech do not have the ability to be the subject of thought, that is, they do not have an independent lexical meaning.

Function words are words that perform a non-nominative function, i.e. they are not names of objects, features, processes, but are used to express relationships between phenomena of reality that have been named significant words, and are used only in combination with the latter [9]. They are immutable (with the exception of the copula), and morphologically indivisible. None of the named functions of function words has a nominative function, but they are used as formal grammatical means of the language: prepositions are introduced in subordinate sentences, and conjunctions are introduced with homogeneous members and in complex sentences.

In foreign linguistics, it is usually not accepted to contrast special auxiliary parts of speech with significant parts of speech, but sometimes they highlight, for example, the category of relative words, which includes articles, prepositions, and conjunctions (while particles are considered a subtype of adverbs).

Function words in English serve to connect words in a phrase or for their grammatical (syntactic) characteristics and are unable to act independently as

members of a sentence. In accordance with their meaning, function words in English are divided into the following groups [4]:

I. Restrictive function words in English: only, just, but, alone, solely, merely, barely, etc.

II. Strengthening the meaning: simply, still, just, yet, all, only, quite, even, etc.

III. Connecting conjunctions: too, also

IV. Negative function words in English: not, never.

Almost all function words in English have analogues in other parts of speech (they are homonyms), for example, with adverbs (simply), conjunctions (but), pronouns (all), adjectives (only). But there are also function words in English that have no analogues in other parts of speech: else, solely, merely.

Describing the polysemy of lexical units (and primarily words) is one of the most difficult tasks of lexical semantics. The main issues in the scientific description of the polysemy of lexical units are related to determining the boundaries of this category. Basic theoretical problems in this area can be formulated as

(a) distinguishing between homonymy and polysemy (i.e., establishing the boundaries within which it is reasonable to talk about different meanings of the same word, as opposed to cases in which we are dealing with different words that have the same form) and

(b) distinguishing between polysemy and monosemy (i.e. establishing the limit to which the difference in specific uses of a word can be considered as a context-dependent variation within one meaning, as opposed to cases when the next use of a word should be described as the implementation of a different meaning).

Determining the boundaries of the category of polysemy - both in parameter (a) and in parameter (b) - does not lend itself to clear operationalization. A

significant amount of research has been devoted to the search for criteria that make it possible to distinguish between polysemy and homonymy, on the one hand, and polysemy and monosemy, on the other. However, any of the proposed criteria, taken separately, is only relative [7].

CONCLUSIONS

Traditionally, the distinction between individual meanings of a polysemantic word (also called sememes or lexical-semantic variants) is carried out on the basis of the criterion of presence - the absence of common semantic features in the compared units. If necessary, a reconstruction automatically occurs in the consciousness of that fragment of reality with which one of the meanings of a given linguistic sign is associated, and, conversely, a native speaker is able to reproduce the linguistic sign with which the perceived fragment of reality is associated. From a logical point of view, any meaning of a polysemantic word is the result of the primary use of the direct meaning of this word, that is, there is continuity between the primary meaning and secondary meanings.

References:

1. Goffman, T.V. Conceptualization of space in the semantics of prepositions: Theoretical and experimental study of prepositions above, above, above, above, above: dis. ...cand. Philol. Sciences: 02.10.19 / Goffman Tatyana Viktorovna. – Moscow, 2005
2. Jespersen O. Philosophy of Grammar / O. Espersen. – Moscow: Foreign Literature Publishing House, 2011. – 285 p.
3. Zhigadlo V.N. Modern English / V.N. Zhigadlo, I.P. Ivanova, L.L. Iofik. – M.: 2016
4. Ilyish B.A. Modern English. Theoretical course / B.A. Ilish. – M.: 2019
5. Kubryakova E.S. In search of the essence of language: Cognitive research / E.S. Kubryakova. – M.: Znak, 2015

6. Litvinov P.P. Prepositions. Increasing speech readiness in English / P.P. Litvinov. – M.: 2004
7. Painter T.N. Conceptualization of space and semantics of English spatial prepositions and adverbs. M., 2016
8. Sweet H. A New English Grammar, Logical and Historical / Henry Sweet. – Oxford, 2010. – 152 p.
9. Smirnitsky A.I. Syntax of the English language. M.: 2017